

Interview transcript STE *Education*

Interview date: 23.05.2023

Participants: P1, P2

I [00:00:01] Yes. Okay. Perfect. Um, yeah. So timewise. So I planned around 15 minutes for, like, an introduction around and also explanation of the methodology. Then 16 minutes, 60 minutes for the interview itself. And then in the end, 15 minutes again for reflection and also feedback. Is this okay if we take one and a half hours? Um, yeah. or do you have any time constraints?

P1 [00:00:31] No, no. And I counted on one and a half hours.

I [00:00:35] Perfect. Okay. Yeah. So maybe I quickly introduce myself again. Um, yeah, so I'm I [interviewer]. I'm currently studying at the University of Osnabrück, and the program is called Environmental Systems and Resource Management. And, yeah, will write my master's thesis together with the Institute of Climate Impact Research. And that's how I got in touch with P2 and also with you. And, um. Yeah, and I'm just interested in agriculture because it's kind of combines for me, social and environmental processes. And I have a feeling that especially regenerative agriculture can have a really big impact regarding different problems that we are currently facing, like climate change, biodiversity crisis, water storage crisis and so on. Yeah, And so maybe now you could quickly introduce yourself. Um, yeah, with your professional background and your relation to regenerative agriculture. Um, I don't know who wants to start.

P2 [00:01:43] I will start then. So really quickly, I think we all sort of know each other, but my background is in sustainability. Future planet studies was my study and then a sort of like design study with ORGANISATION together, which are all focused, which are all into interdisciplinary studies focused on where I personally focused on food. Then I started the different things in the NGO world. I currently I'm working as a farmer. We have 150 or we manage 150 bull cows, bulls, from the age of a few weeks to three years. 500 chickens and a vegetable garden and a summer pop up restaurant. And I'm working throughout regeneration. And that is some other projects every now and then in nature inclusive farming and ranching. And I'm a bit busy. That's why I was also a bit late and then my computer crashed.

P1 [00:03:06] Well, I'm P1. I have a background in literary and cultural analysis and in writing, creative writing to be specific, poetry. I have also a background in working for a sustainable startup. Sustainable startup emphasis on the quotation marks for sustainable (incomprehensive), working in greening greening practices in delivery and consumer goods handling. PERSONAL INFORMATION. So I work on different projects to so do that and receive we receive people on the farm, which is also

a demonstration for, people, groups and companies to take them along into the journey of regeneration and regenerative agriculture. I guess that's enough.

I [00:04:43] Perfect. Thank you. It's just also for me to know with whom I'm talking in the end.

P1 [00:04:49] Of course.

I [00:04:50] Yes. So now I will quickly explain the objectives of the interview. So I think you both already know that we have like different topics. And today we're focusing on education. And for me, education has kind of two pillars at the moment. So one is really like education for the public and especially like school education and university education. And the other pillar is farmers education. And they are both kind of part of this, this topic. And yeah, the goal is really to find out how exactly the interventions or the elements that were collected last year in the during the Earth Day, how they're like them, how they contribute to enabling conditions to transition to regenerative agriculture. And I just decided for a definition of regenerative agriculture, and I know there is like a lot of debates around it. And at one point I got the feedback, okay, it's maybe nice to have a definition. And so if you have really huge objections, of course we can discuss it, but otherwise I would prefer to leave it as it is and just continue. But I will quickly post it in the chat. So. Can you read it?

P1 [00:06:26] Ah wat it's in the of chat.

I [00:06:27] Yeah, it's in the upper left corner. There's like in German "Öffentlicher Chat". So a public chat. And if you click on that button you can open like an extra tap and then you can read it.

P2 [00:06:41] That's the definition of (incomprehensible) [name of a person], I just had a meeting once.

I [00:06:49] That's nice. Yeah. I mean, there are so many different definitions and I just decided for the interviews to take this one. Yeah.

I [00:07:04] It's okay?

P2 [00:07:05] Yeah.

P1 [00:07:07] I mean, I guess it's a definition of regenerative agriculture. And you can't really hurt by this.

I [00:07:17] Yeah, I just. I read so many papers who say, okay, it's not really defined and there is no real definition. So I think it's hard to define. Um. Yeah.

P2 [00:07:31] The holistic part of it is nice that it describes, right? Like socio socioeconomic dimensions.

P1 [00:07:37] Yeah. Yeah.

I [00:07:40] Nice. Okay, so we go with that. And. And I already quickly explained it to P1 earlier. So the goal is really to have mind maps for each of these topics. And in the end, I want to combine these mind maps and look at all the different topics together. Um, yeah, that's, that's for the goals. And now I will share my screen and explain you the methodology. Mm. And it might be a little bit small, but you can put that on full screen and then it's a little bit easier to read. And I will also zoom in later and and always let me know, if you can't read anything, then I would try to zoom in.

P2 [00:08:35] Works out like this.

I [00:08:36] Yeah? Nice okay. And so, first of all, the explanation of the interview set up. So I decided to put the all the elements in three categories. So there are interventions, and intervention is really a collection of elements that were named during the workshops last year. Um, so maybe a little bit condensed, but yeah, basically it's the same interventions that were named last year. And then the second category, these are conditions, or I call them conditions, and these are elements that I extracted also from the workshops last year, but also from literature. And they are considered to enable social tipping to happen or enables a transition to regenerative agriculture and maybe to explain the difference again. So a condition really needs to be fulfilled so that the transitioning process can happen. And that's the idea behind it. And an example would be that there is an increasing public knowledge on a regenerative agriculture, and an intervention is something that would trigger a process that lead to the fulfilment of these conditions, for example, having more non formal and practical education. So it's really a measure that we could implement to get to the conditions that need to be fulfilled. And the third category are the consequences and this is kind of a free space for all possible elements that results from the conditions. So what happens if the conditions are fulfilled? Um, and in the interview we would go through these three categories step by step, or at least we would try to do this and but we will also look at all of them together. And in the workshop last year, there were a lot of elements that were collected. So in this interview, I would really like to focus on also on the interconnections between the elements. So identify links between interventions, conditions and consequences, but also identify links within each category. So for example, between the interventions themselves or between the conditions themselves. But of course, it's also possible to add new elements. So if you think there is something missing, we could

always add this. So it's still super free. Um, for building these connections, I would like to follow a certain yeah, um, methodology so there two kind of arrows and an arrow always shows the influence from one barrier between another. And yeah, positive arrow means that if one one variable increases, so in this case A increases also B increases. And if A decreases, B decreases. So both variables change in the same direction. And a negative arrow would mean that if A increases, B decreases and if A decreases, B increases. So they would change in opposite direction. In most of the case, we will have positive arrows because we were talking a lot about interventions. And so an example would be okay if the public knowledge on regenerative agriculture increases, we could assume that also more people would recognize values for nature, agriculture and food and an example, for a negative arrow. So there is not nothing existing yet. But if we would imagine that no education will happen, we could imagine that public knowledge on regenerative agriculture would decrease. Um, and the idea is really that you discuss with each other and talk and brainstorm together how we could build this map and I would draw the map. And. Yeah, so that's a methodology. And do you have any questions or is it clear?

P2 [00:12:49] I think it's clear.

P1 [00:12:53] I think it's clear, yeah. So, this is what we are going to be talking about, these notes.

I [00:13:02] That's like kind of an inspiration. But if you have other things in mind, we can definitely. It's just like, I'm sorry. My starting point was a collection of elements from the Earth Day last year. But if you think now, okay, there is something missing regarding education, we can definitely add this. Just like it's just that we don't start from scratch and have to do everything again. So also to have a bit of inspiration.

P1 [00:13:35] I have to say that with education of farmers, I have a very, very, very clear opinion and perspective. I think, okay, but collaboration between different stakeholders. I mean, that's always required to get anywhere right with anything.

P2 [00:13:57] I could maybe clarify that part of it. I think yeah we will work out.

I [00:14:08] And do you need maybe a little time to read through all the existing post-its or did you already do that?

P1 [00:14:51] Yes. Okay. I'm up to speed. Yeah.

I [00:15:01] Okay. Perfect. So I would like to start with the conditions. And so it's really about the question, what is needed to accelerate the transition to regenerative agriculture with regard to the

education system. And yeah, I already decided for some conditions that I consider as relevant or that were mentioned last year. And, and for me the focus is really on this knowledge part. But yeah, the question is if you think if there are other conditions that are necessary that need to be reached in terms of education to enhance the transition process.

P1 [00:15:42] Other conditions. Well.

P2 [00:15:47] If you could zoom in a little bit, then that in green is the conditions, right?

I [00:15:52] Yeah.

P2 [00:15:54] Okay.

P1 [00:15:55] So if we think or any conditions are missing here. Yes.

I [00:15:58] Mm hmm. Yeah. Yeah.

P1 [00:16:03] Uh, well, actually. What I do miss here. I think. Yeah. Also, I think there's a lot of, um, power play within education. Um. In the sense of companies like Bayer and Unilever investing in universities and in, in agricultural education institutes. I think it's quite might also be in a condition that that's be illegalized or reviewed or somehow, you know because I think that that's that's like a complete. Or somehow these institutes are are devalued. But I think that's a longer trajectory than. But I don't know how you feel about that, P2, but I think that's quite a no.

P2 [00:17:05] And I'm really thinking about this because I did this this organic agriculture courses in Wageningen. And there was this teacher, but he was like. Um, um. Uh, he was sort of fighting against the structure you're explaining. And so while doing that, he was so fake. I was like, can't we like measure or what's happening with everything underneath, like in the soil? But he described it as a sort of magic we cannot, um, I magic. So, I guess, um, even at certain points, brought an apple to the class and said, yeah, he was going to sort of show us the energetic field of the apple. So he made his really a bit spiritual, which was stupid, I thought, because if that's the opposite of this structure you're fighting against, then, then you're going to make it a sort of, um, you can prove it, that it's possible, that whole regenerative agriculture thing. Right. Um. I'm not sure what to think about that, but I was really amazed I didn't finish the course because I really hated it. I was like, we can measure this. But that's also sort of the, um, the problem. I think that you have to play with this uncertainty and then you have some teacher or knowledge institutes that try to grasp it. Um, for example, doing [?] bulls and regenerative grazing, they're like, yeah, we're not really sure if this is good for biodiversity. We don't have figures yet, so it's not true until we have proof of it. And then the

other the opposite, this organic agroforestry [?] wave through Wageningen, they are like making a sort of mystical and that's also another direction. It's more like even though, um, so yeah, it's sort of, um, philosophical thing maybe or it's a whole new system or new structure. You have to play with uncertainty. I don't know if this says anything, if this means anything for you, but I think I'm.

P1 [00:19:32] It's like them. It's like. I mean, I think what I would relate to this is like the paradigm shift that is necessary in order to see the full value of of regenerative agriculture, which is for some teachers, they are like embracing it by being like, we don't have to prove anything. It's not possible. And then others are like.

P2 [00:19:47] And it's so beautiful.

P1 [00:19:48] cannot prove it and we cannot. So it's not valid or something like there's no in-between there. Is that what you mean?

P2 [00:19:56] Yeah. So we need to have like another an out of system perspective. So it's not even about knowledge because in this current system, knowledge is sort of going these two directions, generally speaking. And then you have other from Bodemzicht. She's like, Come here, measure things. Do your thing. Yeah, if you want to in your system that's important, go for it. But imagine you have to measure everything, what's happening in the soil of a regenerative farm. Um, so it's a bit about trust and yeah, about another paradigm maybe.

P1 [00:20:35] And even being in the sense of that you don't have to research it, but you can trust that it is right. Or what do you mean by that?

P2 [00:20:43] Well, if you have to um, often in this agricultural debates they're like, yeah, we do not know for sure. So for example, in the animal welfare, um, uh, the law we have been talking about in the Netherlands. What was it calls again?

P1 [00:21:06] The animal welfare. You mean the one from, from the ?, that was like almost illegalize all of the things in that industry like.

P2 [00:21:15] Go from zero to Saturday people to like Yeah. (incomprehensive - Dutch expression). So sorry. So there was this conference and other agricultural partners were talking to each other and they were saying yes, but we are not sure if the calf really wants to go outside. We do not have proof that it's relevance to be outside and inside. And then everybody, also the scientists from Wageningen were like, Yeah, that's true. We do not have proof because we cannot test that or measure that. And I think this is one of the stupid mistakes they make all the time. Stupid things they actually hide

behind. But I think a lot that comes from regenerative agriculture things. It will take a really, really long time until we can actually measure it. So how do you deal with that part?

I [00:22:10] Mm hmm.

P1 [00:22:11] But that's also like that in the sense of like saying that we can only know it if we can measure it. Well, so many things we have measured and thought we knew are also slowly turning out to not really be so true. So it's also like, to what extent is measurement indeed like the actual answer? I mean, I guess it's kind of negates complexity, in my opinion, those kinds of experiments. And it can still show interesting proof, I guess, to people that need to be convinced. And in that way, I do understand all that in the sense of like, is there more proof necessary than the proof you can see with your own eyes?

P2 [00:22:54] Yeah. I definitely get that as well. Um, but it's also a bit about. Not sure if I'm really going in a strange direction now, but but I think "We are the regeneration" or M. specifically wants to do is also get the make regeneration something which is like interesting in a sort of societal way something you want to belong to. Because although you I mean the whole climate science proof is there, knowledge is there but other people doing. Um. So it's maybe also something he tries to with "We are the regeneration" and to get the social wave from up and running as well.

P1 [00:23:47] So that is like necessary also within education you think or that's to see.

I [00:23:54] So yeah.

P1 [00:23:56] Maybe it does make people more willing to move away from the things that they have always learned and have always been taught to cling on to like proof and experiments in that sense like to see them as the sole and only proof way of proving anything.

P2 [00:24:16] For example, this whole.

I [00:24:18] No just quickly interrupted the last thing you said. So you want people finding regenerative agriculture interesting. So to make it attractive. And if I would added as a condition, would it be a activity of regenerative agriculture or how would you phrase that?

P2 [00:24:44] Um. Something like that. I mean, um,.

P1 [00:24:47] I guess it's. Maybe it's like more pulling the core values of regenerative agriculture out of like the whole wool and socks and sandals image that it has always have and then making it. Cool.

P2 [00:25:07] Yeah making it something you want to be part of.

I [00:25:10] Yeah. Okay.

P1 [00:25:10] And instead of like, you know, hanging on the edge of the street with a can of Red Bull wanting to hang out on a farm and everything in the middle of nowhere.

I [00:25:20] I will um making it cool.

P2 [00:25:25] I make it. Yeah. And also make it something which other people value as important. For example, my grandma, she said, Hey, super nice that you are a farmer now, but what, why did you do this whole studies and Master's actually so much. And that's the bit of the feeling, right, of the society.

I [00:25:45] Yeah,okay.

P1 [00:25:48] I's also, yeah, I guess the condition is that's a very super important point, like a big condition of, of facilitating like more education of farmers, but also like change in other education and the like regenerating other forms of education, but especially especially educating other farmers. The condition for that is that we start seeing being a farmer as being something cool and something that you can live off of, and that's going to work. So because it's still got an image of like it's not really attainable because you have to be born into a farming family with the billions of billions of cows and otherwise you're not going to get there. And it's not really cool either, you know, It's like.

P2 [00:26:40] Yeah, why would you do that?

P1 [00:26:41] Yeah, why would you want to be a farmer? You're just going to be living in debt your whole life. I guess that's kind of.

P2 [00:26:48] It's a bit of a shame also, right? Because you did, you finished your whole studies and then.

P1 [00:26:54] You went to university. So you're with your brain on.

P2 [00:26:56] on on farming.

P1 [00:26:59] Well, that's like, yeah. So it's also really valuing (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) how you call that. Trade craft.

P2 [00:27:08] And craftsmanship. Craftsmanship. Something like that.

I [00:27:12] Craftsmanship. Okay. Yeah.

P1 [00:27:14] Okay. Yeah. Yeah. Okay. Because also. I would say a part of regenerative agriculture is also localization. Or this.

P2 [00:27:27] Yeah. Yeah.

P1 [00:27:29] And like, sticking to your local communities. That like. That's the main focus. Um. That also requires local production, not only production, but also and consumption. But also they call into the craftsmanship to turn your production into something you can sell. Conserving onion.

P2 [00:27:54] And what works for example, with. So in the Netherlands we have the Warmonderhof [<https://warmonderhof.nl>], which is like the biodynamic educational institutes. And that's really it's really small in the sense of I'm not sure how many people they have here, but it's a sort of thing right. Ah you did the Warmonderhof. So you're and that's really cool in certain social circles. Mm hmm. But still Warmonderhof is I think something else, then. regenerative agriculture is about because biodynamic.

P2 [00:28:31] Mm hmm.

P2 [00:28:33] Yeah. It's different, a different mindset, I think. At least. What do you think?

P1 [00:28:43] I. I agree. I mean, I. We have a students farmer at our farm right now. Student farmer at our farm. And she's doing the learning trajectory for regenerative farming this year. And she's also doing Warmonderhof. And sometimes she tells us about things she learned in class, and I'm quite shocked by it.

P2 [00:29:07] Like?

P1 [00:29:08] Well, the last she told there was the whole class focused on like very anthroposophical view of farming, which is very much human on top. And all animals, all animals don't feel emotion, don't feel pain, don't feel, you know like. It's like, okay, well, I don't really know how to get across today, but that's intriguing. Very much like human on top everybody else below. So like.

P2 [00:29:37] Okay one commenter that. There was. We had a diner this Saturday and there was somebody who was almost finishing their educational studies at Warmonderhof and she said something really funny and she was like, Hey, why do you keep the bulls outside all day long? Because she wants them to go back into the barn, right, to give their manure. I was like ah, no, no, no, no. The only reason for that is that we want animals to behave as natural as possible and be outside and graze and have natural behaviour. And only when it's winter and the press kind of handler feels kind of. And then we take them inside and indeed use the manure for grapes for. But I was like. Yeah. It's also it's almost the end of May. Of course the animals are outside.

I [00:30:48] Okay so it's quite interesting. I just tried to like go back to the education part. So I think that aspect of localization is super interesting. There is another social tipping element which is called. So I would put it a bit apart and try to focus more on education. And so I added from what you said, like, okay, the attractivity a little bit. And also combined with that, this image, the cool image of being a farmer. I didn't find another phrasing and I also added, I think that's what you said at the beginning. P2, the trust in regenerative agriculture and this aspect of, okay, if there is no proof, it's hard sometimes hard to see or how to say that regenerative agriculture is good. And so I added this paradigm shift in believing, I don't know, it's a little bit abstract, but I was not sure how to frame it differently.

P1 [00:31:47] I understand. I also think it maybe is a revaluing of history, maybe because we there's so many people around the globe that have been doing regenerative agriculture, like without knowing that it would ever be called regenerative agriculture, you know, But just because that's the way that they their culture was, was based on living together with another ecosystem, I think is also if we start seeing more that it's always been there and that we've always been doing it like we've always been growing food this way, but well, also feeding other other life. I think that's also helped. So it's also maybe, maybe that's also like maybe that that helps in this paradigm shift in believing it's like, it's like decolonize history. Decolonizing our view of agriculture and then what it means to be a farmer.

I [00:32:43] Okay. Nice.

P2 [00:32:44] And also maybe one one thing to add to that trust. Um, people also have a paradigm shift. Um. A lot of people in the Netherlands think certain landscapes are really nice and beautiful. Well, they actually are degraded and they actually if you learn more and more, they actually are really ugly. Yeah. Um so it's also, it's trust but also.

P1 [00:33:14] But also kind of revealing the ideology Both.

I [00:33:19] Yeah. Mm.

P1 [00:33:20] It's very true. Yeah.

P2 [00:33:23] You start to attach different images to what is a beautiful landscape and what is not.

P1 [00:33:29] Um. Mm hmm. Yeah.

I [00:33:32] So also like.

P1 [00:33:34] Reframing reality.

I [00:33:36] Or having like, having another lens in a way so that you don't see like a nice field of raps and it's yellow. I mean, it happened to me actually. I really loved I don't rapes, but I don't know if it's the same. This yellow plant, which is. I really like it. It's super beautiful. But I think it's also not like a super nice field often. So. So but how would you like, phrased it in a conditional way? Like what? What is it like? People need to have like another.

P1 [00:34:09] I guess it requires kind of at least kind of knowing what's going on in the field. Like what if you grow something? I don't know. How do you phrase this and that briefly, because.

P2 [00:34:23] I'm gonna give one more example. Maybe that helps. When I was when I was traveling to Central America, when I was like 19, I thought it was my first time in the in the rainforest in Costa Rica. And I was like, super cool. I've been in the rainforest and met all these pictures. And then I was with a biology teacher and she was like really sad after my first jungle trip because she was like, There were no native species there. So she showed me something. She saw exactly the same things, but she saw something completely different.

P2 [00:35:02] I think that's.

P1 [00:35:04] But that's like knowing. And like, I think that's about knowing your your community, that's non-human. You know, it's like in the Netherlands, we get taught that seeing acres and acres of grassland, short grassland. It's like, oh my God, look how green our country is. We're doing so well. Well, really, it's degraded soil. So it's knowing that how like who is growing in that field and how do they actually thrive. So it's like getting to know what's behind what's really happening. I don't know. It's like it's like putting if I keep thinking of this movie where this guy buys glasses and then suddenly sees all advertisements, capitalist advertisements, happens, and he sees like, spend money, think you're cool, think you're sexy if you buy these glasses, You know, he sees like a

subliminal message. It's kind of like seeing the subliminal message of ecosystems and like, we're maybe like the lack of diversity in the ecosystem ecosystems.

I [00:36:06] I don't know, how to phrase it.

P1 [00:36:08] It's hard to, but it's.

P2 [00:36:11] Good that you record it.

P1 [00:36:12] It requires kind of I think to know or getting introduced to the complexity of life, I would say and of ecosystems.

I [00:36:20] I mean, there's already.

P2 [00:36:21] Making new links actually between what's what you perceive as beautiful and making new links between your images and knowledge, right?

P1 [00:36:33] Unlearning.

P2 [00:36:34] Yeah, Unlearning.

I [00:36:36] I mean, there's already is a post-it about public knowledge. I mean, it's a little bit broad, but I would maybe just put it below because it's kind of specifying what kind of knowledge is needed for me. Okay.

P1 [00:36:50] And it's Yeah.

I [00:36:52] So and that's. Yeah. Sorry.

P1 [00:36:56] Doesn't that also kind of I've two things acutally, one that I already wanted to say a little while ago regarding like the cool image of being a farmer and attractivity. Attractivity. Um. Regarding Yeah, let's just do that one. I think I was talking to someone on Earth Day, actually this past Earth Day, and they said that they knew a lot of people, and I've actually heard it a lot since then. A lot of people would be interested, for instance, in being a farmer, but that the the, the lack of perspective in getting access to land, especially for people of color in the Netherlands, was like a big, big, big, big demotivator for people to even look into it or even think of the possibility of becoming a farmer or taking it seriously. I think that might also really be a condition that that those that that is

that becomes more accessible, that land becomes more accessible to actually fully facilitate this transition.

I [00:37:59] Yes. So land access is also another, another big topic. And but I will add to this because it's also.

P1 [00:38:14] I do think it's a condition for it to really work.

I [00:38:19] Yeah. But that's, it's actually super nice to already have some links from the interview so I don't even need to find them in a complicated way. It's okay. So if you don't have anything to add to the conditions, I would like to go to the interventions, if that's okay for you. I mean, we already mixed up it a little bit.

P1 [00:38:40] I have one more condition.

I [00:38:42] Yeah, go ahead.

P1 [00:38:46] Well, it's really related to public knowledge and regenerative agriculture. It also kind of requires public knowledge on other forms of agriculture, because a lot of people don't understand why regenerative agriculture is in general necessary now, because we have bio products and they have no idea. Maybe it's like the. The fact that we do not have any idea about what's going on on farms, most people and have any idea or have any idea of how things are grown and the fact that like a bio potato is still like super plowed, probably sprayed landscape and then also is like, that's it. You don't really think that you need to look into anything new if you don't even know that the like the supposedly good things are also not as great as you would maybe like them to be.

P2 [00:39:38] And maybe also what I for example last thing. Well, I was doing this introduction to this documentary on (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) about the soil. And then people in the end were asking me and another farmer, okay, but what can we do? So I make this super cynical, I guess, super cynical reaction. Like, yeah, you know, there's this whole whole network of organic shops all throughout the Netherlands, there are many, in Utrecht and they at least do less harm to the environment and you maybe, maybe even you can find some regenerative products there. I was like, that's the easiest way to go. And otherwise you can look at this, this or this networks and they have all maps of farmers you can go to and visit and buy your food directly there. And if that's too much work, I completely understand. But most of the bigger cities in the Netherlands have organic shops you can go to. So it's really pretty easy. And then everybody was a bit like. Yes, it's not super hard. Although organic is not perfect, of course. But I think, you know. It's if you, if you want to do

something and everybody was like, oh, we want to do something. But I'm super sure that only eat food with pesticides. So.

I [00:40:58] So, yeah, nice. It's super interesting, what you are saying. I mean, very good. Yes. I would really like to go to the interventions and I don't know, I thought it would maybe make sense to start either with the farmers or with the public and. And look at the interventions for. Yeah. Either of them and then the others, because I have a feeling they're like these two groups, but I don't know what you think, if it would make sense.

P1 [00:41:35] I just. I think it's easy to separate them probably.

I [00:41:39] Okay, so should we start with the farmers?

P1 [00:41:44] Like.

I [00:41:45] Okay, so, I mean, the only 2 to 3 interventions that I captured from the workshops last year regarding this was like a really general thing on education of farmers, which is kind of super broad. And I would really like to know if you have any ideas or more specific ideas of how this education of farmers could look like or what kind of interventions are there to enhance education of farmers. Um. And then there just like, yeah, the collaborations between different stakeholders and experimental outside spaces um, but of course if you have ideas, yeah, let me know.

P1 [00:42:29] Maybe it's good to talk about the "Regeneratieve school" a bit, because I think it's an example of an intervention that we are doing now together with farmers. Um. The regenerative school is a decentralized learning network that we've started building up, by like a couple of farmers have joined in hands with, so with a couple of foundations to make sure that we can start building up a decentralized and bound to the ground learning network where both people, both inspiring regenerative farmers, as well as established farmers want to transition, can actually find the locations in which the farmer is themselves sharing their knowledge and within their own farm context. And the reasoning behind this for us is that there's so many. Like when you're learning about agriculture in the in the agricultural schooling institutions, like to what extent are you actually on a farm or being taught by a farmer? Um, and who else do we trust more to teach us what we think we need to know other than the experience, like the bodily experience person that actually is themselves existing from farming and especially farming, regeneratively or transitioning and making it relatable for you to transition. So I think that's like a I think this is a necessary intervention myself because it takes the power away from like it's it's a it's a it's an equal network of natural places where farmers are teaching farming or explaining farming or sharing their knowledge and experience in farming and also within their specific context so that everybody, of course themselves has a different context from either

where they want to start from farm, how they would want to run a farm, who they would want to include on their farm, or who they already have presence at their farm. So it will also it will also enable a cow farmer that wants to transition to visit a regenerative cow farmer instead of visiting a random regenerative farm with chickens, like Bodemzicht and a vegetable garden and an agroforestry system. And we don't know anything about inheriting cows because we never have. So it also facilitates like really context specific knowledge sharing, which I also think is really, really important, especially in regenerative agriculture, because it really acknowledges the context specificity of every individual that's a part of it.

I [00:45:16] Mm hmm.

P1 [00:45:18] So that was a little rant. I hope you could keep up with the notes.

P2 [00:45:23] But, um, yeah, I just.

P1 [00:45:26] You have a lot of.

I [00:45:28] I tried to capture the, like, key words a bit and will listen to it again after afterwards. Um. But that's actually super nice. So for me, the question would be, how's this is so this would be linked to the conditions.

P2 [00:45:44] So, um.

I [00:45:47] Yeah. Sorry.

P2 [00:45:48] Only a question. So we have. We have, like, a division in this conditions part, which was like, farmers and like.

I [00:45:55] And university schools. Like, more the public, like more general knowledge dissemination, yeah.

P2 [00:46:04] Ok, maybe it's good for the farmers, to make division in between new farmers and existing farmers. Because that's a huge difference. And I think because a lot of, most of the education which you currently see like agroforestry, permaculture courses and they're all focusing on this new type of farmers.

P1 [00:46:32] And this helps not really on assisting established farmers to transition. Yeah.

I [00:46:37] So okay, so maybe an intervention. I just oh sorry, my computer is slow at the moment, but maybe an intervention would be like what would it be courses for existing farmers. But how would these courses look like? So what is, what kind of knowledge is needed there? Or it has to transferred there?

P2 [00:47:01] How to attract new farmers?

I [00:47:03] No, for the old farmers, I think you. Yeah.

P2 [00:47:05] For old farmers. Well I think for the old farmers um, the, the system needs to be different. Right. So um, if they. For example, if you have like a to (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) meet up about something content specific type of knowledge exchange day, even organized by other farmers which are like not conventional, but big farms which have been a farm for a long time. But they always do is that it's um, you need to take a day off as a farmer, which is quite hard to do and do quite a lot of effort. And when it's organized by another farmer in the same like who has been a farmer for a long time, then they understand how other farmers work. But if you go to yes, um, get your ah yeah, I'd say knowledge exchange days captured by the new type of farmers. Um, the only people who come there most of the time do not own land or do not have access to land. Um, so there's something happening there which I think I think you should pay people who have a lot of access to land or manage a lot of land, you should pay them for attending education because it already costs them money to go away. Um, and also this kind of knowledge days, they're organized by a bit idealistic people and they're like, if they're so at least 50 people coming we are really happy and ah okay, not a lot of real farmers showed up, but at least we had a nice group of people together and they're not acknowledging all the time that, um, they're like, Yeah, it's free, right? It's free for farmers to come, but it's not free for them to come. They managed a lot of land. They're like stewards of their land. So they, uh, yeah, I'm not sure if my.

P1 [00:49:27] I think it, yeah, I think in general financial compensation for farmers that are already operating as a farmer, I wouldn't say even if you're, if you just started you know. If you are a new farmer it should be, I think it should be compensated because that's true. True investment. If for years having sustainable. Making the making farming practices more sustainable rather than just throwing money at them to build different stables.

P2 [00:49:59] So but I think in terms of condition structures also but so this is one thing, but also in terms of this whole subsidy rules, um, if you're if you're a farmer and you're really good a farmer, you're quite probably not really good at writing subsidy subsidies because it's a way different skill. And so all this people getting this. So yeah, I don't know, the, the condition is that it speaks the same language of the farmer who want to.

P1 [00:50:31] Or there's a different structure you don't have to like because also requesting a subsidy to be able to attend some kind of educational events that will help you change your way of farming or transition away from. That's also investing time and money. I would say that it should be maybe then up to the party that is organizing the the Knowledge facilitation day to make sure that they get subsidy, to give money to farmers, to invite them to come, you know, like reverse the ticket payments.

P2 [00:51:03] You know how this is. You know how this works for the subsidies and the Dutch subsidy culture. If you're a farmer and you're in one of this educational agricultural projects, the maximum you can earn per hours is €50 or €60. And the government says you cannot pay the farmer more. But a consultant can be or an expert can be paid €120 maximum for attending a project.

I [00:51:39] Oh, okay. So you mean in this knowledge exchange projects, if, like, farmers are invited and consultants are invited. Farmers get paid much less.

P2 [00:51:52] Yeah. Yeah. They do not allow you to pay them more than 50 or €60 an hour. Well, they do allow you to put in your financial, your well.

P1 [00:52:07] Your consultant[?].

P2 [00:52:09] Yeah. Yeah.

P1 [00:52:11] Because and I think that's like thinking. That's like also thinking in the backward way, probably results and thinking in the backward way of. Hello. Of thinking that a consultant has a bigger range of effects than a farmer becomes a consultant can talk to multiple farmers, but a farmer will only be talking to their own land. Well that's like completely mean.

I [00:52:35] Mhm.

P1 [00:52:36] The reality of life and but that's also kind of relates like the, the what I said about financing within education. Like the, like I guess that's the condition for I can't find it any more because it's, I think out of view. But we said something about well it's like yeah regenerative friendly financial structures. I think that, I think like as much as we should pay farmers to attend educational events or together. Also, farmers should be compensated way easier for sharing their own knowledge. Mhm. If they post people at their farm or they post educational trajectories for for other farmers. Why is there like a shitty low fee that they gets for having someone get some experience on their farm? Well, going to a big educational institute, they have to pay like €2,000 or more. It's not so good, I would say. So the knowledge sharing, as well as participating in acquiring new knowledge,

should be rewarded because both of them are taking time away from your job and away from financial flow.

P2 [00:54:17] And maybe if you have that and then we go back to the forwards through the education institution, uh, part of the condition intervention question I think this also really goes for universities and research institutes that they, um. And several projects I was working for, I always got this question. It's like, yeah, we want to do this, this, this at the farms or do we want to test the soil or we want to do whatever, whatever, whatever. And my question was always, okay, cool what's, what's in it for the farmer.

P1 [00:54:58] Yeah.

P2 [00:55:00] Yeah. But that doesn't cost a lot of time. We just need to use for this amount of time a piece of land. Want to come by several times and then we have a coffee and we take his time. And. And what does he get back? Yeah. In three years time, you will get a report with all the people on the sandy, clay, soil, and then. And what's his perspective? What can he how do I express this, how can he act upon after that. Yeah. Well it's just the beginning of a research which is part of a way bigger and so there's nothing in it eventually but it will cost him at least a week time. Um and a lot a piece of land he cannot use and, and there are many, many examples of this. Um.

I [00:55:47] So, but what would be the, um, what is the need behind it? So do you think that research should be more farmers, centralized or so? Uh.

P2 [00:56:02] Yeah.

P1 [00:56:03] I think the intention of or like maybe it's, it's also a possibility that with an education people are, are facilitated with some compensation money for the time for the for example the farmer that they are, are making use of, I mean we receive multiple requests for months, to participate in interviews of at least four to five minutes of research. And if you if we would say yes to everyone and add up all that time. It would be quite an investment on our side into the world of research. And in the meantime, we could have been regenerating land, you know, so that sort of thing.

P2 [00:56:48] It's also a shift in thinking, right? So I try to do that all the time. I'm like, okay, that's why. Wait.

P1 [00:56:57] Like the shift in thinking about the value of research. Maybe also like.

P2 [00:57:01] Yeah. But also I'm like, okay, so we have the stewards of our lands and we're gonna actually take their time, so they cannot do something with a that land you don't have access to because that's a problem. And then yeah, and then what do you give them back.

I [00:57:21] Mm hmm.

P2 [00:57:22] Something that cannot act upon. Okay.

I [00:57:25] Okay.

P1 [00:57:25] And something that doesn't really in general. Like what? What's, you know, especially if it's like, we would just want to test the soil to see how good your practices are. Well, if you tell me in three years that their great than thank you so much for taking my time.

P2 [00:57:41] And I've been involved in some of these projects and it's also. But the answer so that a lot of this subsidies is a really big report which is okay if there are something to act upon. Um and I think yeah, sorry, my dog.

P1 [00:58:06] This really relates to. I think this, this regenerative friendly financial structuring in that because this was also really mitigate the word research as well. Because I think a lot of like that's also like no transparency there in terms of most research being done into regenerative agriculture is being funded by parties that are really really really can benefit from these outcomes of research, especially if they can frame them in the way that benefits them. I mean, we I've I've had to tell people that whose PhD was financed by McDonald's that we were not going to give them the secrets of our farm, you know. Or like it's like an interesting thing to even as a researcher, not you can be you seem to be aware of.

I [00:58:55] And also was also your argument to make research more so that the farmer, for example, can get out something out of research are like or is it like I see the point that okay, if farmers participate in research, they should be somehow or should be somehow seen that it's time that we take away from them, for example. That's one point. And the other point, do you also think that for farmers too, it's was my for farmers to have more knowledge in regenerative agriculture is it's like is the research valuable, is the research needed or is the research not important at all? I think that was my.

P1 [00:59:39] I think the research is important. It can be really important and can be really needed. But I think too few researchers ask themselves the question, to what extent is this research relevant for the farmer that I am trying to to request time from to, to be able to do this study, you know.

P2 [01:00:00] And I think that's where regenerative agriculture also makes for difficult is that it's context based. So yeah. And actually. Context so you can never really tell by reading an article, what the best idea is the best idea is always to observe, you know, maybe some like framework or something to to learn from others. But um, yeah. I read many articles, so many things, but I've never read anything about holistic grazing with ? bulls in an sort of sandy poor soil. I have no idea.

I [01:00:55] I see. Yeah.

P1 [01:01:00] Yeah. Yeah, I guess. Yeah. A lot of research, is always trying to find common denominators between all these different super specific contexts. But, yeah. Maybe they should just focus their research on one activity. Yeah. Then it's really, really specific, but.

P2 [01:01:20] I have no idea. But I think also seeing the farmer as the expert instead of.

I [01:01:25] Yeah. Yeah.

P2 [01:01:27] That's. I mean they're the experts. Right. Mhm.

I [01:01:33] But it's also related for me to this point of like allowing farmers to and allowing is not the right word but what you said in the beginning, with this okay farmers teach farmers and. Yeah. And also kind of farmers teach research. Maybe that would be the next step. I mean. To. Yeah. To put the farmer more in the center of it.

P1 [01:02:02] Yeah. I do think that's quite important. Also seeing the political climate. Mhm. And the like. Yeah. I feel like a lot of farmers don't really feel seen.

I [01:02:19] Yeah. Okay.

P2 [01:02:26] So I think it's not to devalue science in general, but it's science in a research for farmers. It's actually only I think personally at the moment, at this moment in time where I'm at with work and farm, I think it's mainly interesting when it's about regulations, then research can really do something for you. So if it's approved that you get more biodiverse land by an holistic grazing scheme. Then you can maybe use your meadows which are have the political destination nature in a different way and that's the interesting parts but.

I [01:03:11] Yeah and can you say it again so research can influence the policy or what was the um.

P2 [01:03:19] Well, I think is it this. For farmers it becomes super interesting when research starts proofing things so they can within the current regulations um prove their point that, for example, holistic grazing is better for the environment than um. Mhm. Than just normal grazing or having grasslands and in the next year corn and ploughing and everything. So if they can proof this kind of things. But I think the common denominator in this one is if it gives the farmer something to act upon.

I [01:03:58] Mhm.

P2 [01:04:00] Or if it's connected linked to an extraordinary proof that what he's doing or she's doing this is better. So you have, you have many of this kind of regulations, you have this goat farmer in the north of the Netherlands and but she does what she does, she makes the most natural raw milk cheeses but also with the natural way, not wait.

P1 [01:04:33] Hay.

P2 [01:04:34] No it's the thing you make cheese with and it has a name. You get it from the stomach of the animal rights.

I [01:04:45] Lap in German.

P1 [01:04:47] Rennet.

P2 [01:04:48] Yeah. Yeah. So but she so she has the most natural process all and balance with nature as she's produced from the rennet, from her own goats or from the milk goats, whatever you call them. But she's not allowed to kill them herself and she's not allowed actually to use her own rennet by law. Um, um, but if she can, I think what this kind of farmers needs, just one example is that she can prove that what she's doing is good for the environment. And if she has scientific proof of that, that's what she does is, uh, is connected to linked or to that ecosystem she's working on. I think these are the things regenerative farmers who already benefits from.

I [01:05:37] Mhm.

P2 [01:05:38] In terms of science, um. Maybe it's a bit for off from the topic.

I [01:05:48] I mean, I think for me, research was always a little bit in between. Like research was for me not clear to which social tipping element it belongs. So I think it's quite fine to, to add it here then. Um yeah, so my question is, do you have more interventions regarding the farmers or should we go to the more public related interventions?

P1 [01:06:18] I mean, let me think. Interventions for the farmers.

I [01:06:24] I have the feeling you already said a lot, But if you can think of something else, I don't want to, like, cut you off. That's why I'm asking.

P1 [01:06:37] No, I think. I think for now. Shared up out. Out of sharing.

I [01:06:47] Okay. Nice. So if we try to organize it a little bit here. I'm sorry. It's always getting super messy.

P1 [01:06:58] I'm really impressed that you are even capable to keep this up.

I [01:07:03] And so I think I will zoom in down here a little bit because we have the public here and the public knowledge and also the interventions that are more related to the public. So one big aspect was like influencing the curricula of on different educational levels. And then there was a part about non-formal and practical education, trainings for teachers, also general questioning the objectives of school and education. And also, again, the resources, which I see is a direct link to the regenerative friendly financial structure. Um. Yeah, but so what do you think? What are important interventions to inform, to create knowledge within the public, within the larger public?

P1 [01:08:00] We started with school gardens.

P2 [01:08:05] Yeah.

I [01:08:06] Sorry. Can you repeat it?

P1 [01:08:08] School vegetable gardens?

I [01:08:10] Mm hmm. So this I like an aspect of more non formal practical education. I will add school gardens.

P1 [01:08:23] Yeah. Oh, yeah. Learn to grow. Sorry. It was already here.

I [01:08:28] Yeah, I'm in some super small. Mm hmm.

P1 [01:08:38] Oh, is that an intervention relating to education? I guess so a little bit. I don't know. I'm thinking of. You can tell me if it's relevant or not. I'm thinking of the school. That's high school, which

is right by our farm. Like on the edge of our farm. And on the also on the edge of our farm are two fields which are very much conventionally farmed. And last just last year, were like 17 times sprayed with poison right next to the school. I'm wondering I don't know if it's really relevant 100% for education, but I also think that as an intervention, it should be interventions in education. But I think this school should be trying to sue. But I guess that's no, it's not relevant for this topic.

P2 [01:09:36] Well, it maybe is if you if you have this course, at least I had it in high school in your first or second year, which was called. Okay.

P1 [01:09:48] Yeah. Yeah. Um, like, um, housekeeping.

P2 [01:09:53] Housekeeping. But. But just like, taking care of yourself, basically. And you're.

P1 [01:09:59] How to cook, how to. Yeah.

P2 [01:10:01] Hmm. And what we made during that discourse course was, um, I was like, Oh, that's. We're going to cook. So we made a sandwich with some cheese, butter, lettuce and tomato and an egg. Um. But we can teach people what healthy is about and that people have no idea that, uh. all of the food we are eating. Most of people are eating is completely sprayed with pesticides. That pesticides. If you live in an area where a lot of conventional agriculture takes place, you have a higher risk of Parkinson of certain types of cancer than if you have to there with agricultural fields that has been sprayed with pesticides for a few days in some cases. I mean, I think that could be maybe be taught during this course.

P1 [01:11:09] Yeah. Especially like relating health and eating healthy to planetary health as well. Would be really effective.

I [01:11:19] For me as also to do with this aspect of knowing what is happening around you. So if, like teachers and students see that, like pesticides are directly next to the school, but maybe they just don't realizing it because they're not aware of the fact that it's happening. Um, so maybe it's also related to this.

P2 [01:11:42] Yeah, also training for teachers. And also we should not frame it as sustainability and health are always frames of this things. Um. Yeah. How do I say. They're framed in a wrong way. What's a fun thing about regenerative is, is that it's actually it's not your all the time doing something wrong. And if you do something sustainable, you do not use this one plastic straw and you're doing something good, then it's not. But the whole path of regeneration is something good. Yeah, it's a way more positive mindsets, which you can incorporate in health and sustainability. Because for me

personally they have quite negative associations. Eating healthy also in this organic shops, there is a specific smell, healthy foods, although the cookies for example, have the same amount of sugar, even more. They taste healthy. Um. We can move away from that and just make it nice. Um also in education.

P1 [01:12:54] I think it's also revealing a little bit especially like to be able to cement that like positive, explicitly positive affect every step of the way that you have if you are entering into this regenerative state of being where you try to really engage with with the whole ecosystem around you. Um, I think it's also like a complete necessity is like even if we were to every school would have a vegetable garden and we would all learn how to grow vegetables. Um. I think it's still, it's really and, well, it can be really human centred still. Like we grow vegetables for us and there's no one else enjoying this. We're not doing this for anybody other than ourselves. I think it's still a really good skill to learn that. But I think it's also really important to, like, start educating children from children, children onwards about like the fact that you are a part of this ecosystem, that you are a species that is affecting and has affect and can affect other life and actually can positively affect you also to see the changes that we are making. For instance, I'm always thinking about it like this idea of people who have zero clue where to start gardening, like are really scared to do anything because they're scared to have a negative impact where you just give them like the experimental space. It's also, I think in here somewhere, the space for experiments. Um. Where you just start really small by, for instance, hoeing one part of your garden, one square meter and not doing anything to the other. Where you see, seeing the impact that you can have also by staying away, but also by doing something.

I [01:14:54] Mm hmm.

P1 [01:14:56] I think that. Um. The focus on us being a part of nature, you know, us being this and understanding ourselves as, like, our god health be containing the same, like containing the soil. You know, we are literally like, I think that's like a super big part of, like, teaching. What is healthy also is like, even understanding who we what role we fulfil ourselves because we always ourselves so separate from all this, I think that's like core to also really understand health and also the sense of planetary health.

I [01:15:37] Yeah. I'm not sure how to connect this to everything. I will just move it next to the health part.

P2 [01:15:45] And it maybe also connects to this paradigm.

P1 [01:15:49] Yeah, paradigm shift. Yeah. Definitely. Not even maybe. Definitely. It connects.

I [01:15:57] Nice. Yeah. I will connect this.

P1 [01:16:00] Sorry. I have to let my cat in. Yeah. Sorry. So, you know. All the animals everywhere.

I [01:16:13] Yeah. Um so I'm just wondering, like, how or do you have any ideas how we could achieve this, that we have more health in school and more experimental outside spaces, more practical education for children. So what I mean, maybe it's it's it's just I'm curious if you have any ideas how this could be, um. Yeah. How this could be developed or how this could be more implemented, because it's not the case at the moment.

P2 [01:16:46] I think we just need really what happened with what we should do with the farmers. Make like farming cool again. Teaching also needs to be really cool again. Right. And also the road for a farmer to tell something about farming in front of a class or to, I don't know, make this connection.

P1 [01:17:12] Bring the children to the farm.

P2 [01:17:18] Or bring the farm to children, you know? Mm Yeah. And it sounds like too easy of a solution like low hanging fruit. But I am a geography teacher, so. And I, um, I did a few classes now. I started experimenting a little bit for, in Utrecht, for like 11, 12 year olds and also some things, some classes I gave for groups of seven or eight. And if you talk about the farm and about food mainly, although they have different, um, and educational backgrounds, different cultures they come from, everybody can always get super enthusiastic.

I [01:18:17] Um. Yeah. Mhm. Um.

P1 [01:18:26] I'm actually really feeling, this idea of making farmers teachers literally not only to teach farming. But maybe I'm having brain thought that I'm now throwing into this this conversation. So I'm sorry if that's the case, but, um, I keep thinking about at our farms so many different kinds of people and groups and schools and politicians and everybody wants to visit the farm because everybody wants to be as regenerative farming is like, it's great, I get it. But of course I have to request money for it or and you have to say no a lot because it's so many people. But it's actually I was thinking, especially with schools of children, I think it's really, really, really important that children visit farms and learn also that the farmer is not just a human being, but like all of the beings at the farm were together farming. And I was thinking about how it would be such an amazing way of enabling this better if every farm if it would be possible for a farm to request compensation for being a teacher for a specific group. So, for instance, for a school in the neighborhoods, for instance, for or specifically

for children, and then another one specifically for politicians, I don't know, but that it's like that there's a set up where the farmer is actually considered a teacher. Really. A teacher.

P2 [01:20:14] Yeah. There is this one organisation who does this, this exactly this. So they help you out actually as a farmer with this educational program and different concepts and they even fix the context for, you with the school in the neighborhood, so as school, you can request like a farming education thing.

P1 [01:20:34] Um, how is this called this?

P2 [01:20:38] Yeah. So at the farm here I had four students doing a living lab last year. And my question was how to tell the story of regenerative agriculture to, to, to the city. And they first came up with something like education. Um, and they made really nice connections with different different parties. Um, but then my main problem was like, where do I get the time from. Um. When am I going to do it and who's going to pay for it and what's my goal actually of doing this.

P1 [01:21:20] So that's what, you know, that's like because the farmer's not actually being seen as a teacher.

P2 [01:21:28] No and also it's like giving a education about the farm in a classroom environment is really hard because I know it's really hard, but it needs, you need to prepare and you need to look at pictures and and the other way around getting like a whole high school class or primary school class here. Yeah, that's really expensive because they need to rent a bus most of the times. Um, so I think it, it should be more in the direction of BSL or kindergarten. It's more kind of. I think that's more low hanging fruit than disconnection because there are several organisations doing this. Organisations. Um.

P1 [01:22:22] So you're talking That should be extracurricular.

P2 [01:22:25] Yeah. And for me personally, would just need to make up a lot of new school kind of concepts, high school concepts, where. Which is way more practically based and where, for example, they get used to like food or farming. And from a farm. Imagine you're really not good in math, mathematics or language or whatever, and you can learn it all from farming or like teams education perspective. So if you're really interesting in grow vegetables or having animals, which a lot of children with their cultural, different backgrounds in big cities are, because their parents or your grandparents, they're still living in another country. So they get crazy enthusiastic about the farm concept and if you teach them from that perspective, like basic knowledge, like mathematics. Yeah. That's way more interesting. Context specific research and that there's a few schools doing

this, but the first century Spinoza, Spinoza, 21st, it's High school in Amsterdam has like team specific. Um. Education. I do see I think a lot of, um, I personally put a lot of hope into this kind of educational process. Okay. So that directly links to flexibility in curricula. So this kind of things can be useful.

I [01:24:13] Yeah. And yeah, I kind of gave up a little bit.

P2 [01:24:20] I was just thinking I have no idea what the, um. If not for half a year I'm living here, how you make this education farm education bigger.

I [01:24:32] Yeah, like from what you said, I have a feeling that also kind of the financial structure is needed. I mean, is in the time probably from for teachers to do that. I mean I think school is I don't know how it is in the Netherlands, but in Germany school is super like with a lot of pressure. They have to put a lot of knowledge into the people and through the children. And there's not much space for going here and there.

P1 [01:24:57] But that's also that's a part of the paradigm shift again, right? It's like what is what knowledge should you be cramming and how should you be cramming? Gets into a kids head.

I [01:25:06] Yeah.

P1 [01:25:08] Is it like being at a desk in a in a classroom and putting it on, writing it on the board, or is it by bringing them to the knowledge? It's kind of it's almost like holistic grazing. Are you bringing the food to the animal or are you bringing the animal to the food.

P2 [01:25:25] Or have the animal wants to go to foo itself? The only thing you need to do is move the space.

I [01:25:35] Okay, look at the time. I mean, we are already over the one and a half hours actually.

P1 [01:25:41] It's it's it's I do have to say, I think it's a hard one to crack because, like, it's requires a full reboot of the educational system. So it's like, it's like, how do you know where to start?

I [01:25:55] Yeah, but I have the feeling that's actually for a lot of the topics at the moment that kind of need like a system change to to like and I was like, okay. Maybe that's, that's like the result of my, my thesis that everything needs to change.

P1 [01:26:14] But maybe a final maybe final small comment because I know we're already on time, but it's like. Um. Um, what I've been what we've been doing with the regenerative school, also why

we're creating a decentral school of made up farms where you can learn things. It's not like a separate institutes or like requesting that's, that's existing. But agricultural education starts putting the farmers on the in the classroom. It's because we feel like it also starts with policy to such a large extent in the Netherlands like what is what is educated, what is taught in schools. And it takes such a damn long time to change the curriculum anywhere in any school. So we were it's like there's no time to wait. So it's like just building up. Let's just build a new school and let's just do it differently and maybe at some point we won't be necessary anymore. But I think that's probably key. Just start doing it yourself differently.

P2 [01:27:19] Just I think. I think maybe I find the words to sum that up. It's like context specific. That's what regenerative agriculture is about and where education should be about. Right?

I [01:27:33] Mm hmm. Yeah. Um. Yeah. I don't know. Can I. Can I ask you one last question, and then I'm maybe done? Because for me, it would also be good to know. Maybe it's hard to say it quickly now, but, um, what are the current barriers like I mean, we already talked about it. Policy is too slow, we have not the right financial structures. We have a lack of land, but can you think of something else quickly?

P1 [01:28:10] Yeah, I think. The current paradigm. A big hurdle. Having to explain the nature and agriculture are not different, not separate. There's no. Barrier. Barrier.

P2 [01:28:31] It's really complex. So if we if we that's the solution, but if we visualise it. Like, for example, John, did it with green gold. We need more art, maybe.

P1 [01:28:47] More Art. I love that.

P2 [01:28:49] Like to visualize or to express because it's in words or in in in the way we tend to communicate things like words or in texts. Um, knowledge base that's really hard to understand. So if we can, um.

P1 [01:29:15] That's also the way we use words, I think.

P2 [01:29:18] Yeah. I was thinking you're going to explain this better than I do.

P1 [01:29:24] Well, I think we we, when we use language to create truth or to speak truth or to share like knowledge, we suddenly make it really, really abstract and not personal at all because we believe everything should be objective, which, in my opinion, doesn't exist. Instead of like, instead of sharing embodied knowledge by sharing our embodied stories, like what storytelling do we need with

experience do we need to share to be able to, which is full of knowledge, which super much about decoupling also. I think decolonizing knowledge and like the validity of knowledge, what is valuable, what is valid. But that's a whole other chapter we are opening here.

I [01:30:09] No, but it's good.

P2 [01:30:12] By the way, in the meantime, I'm getting a What's App message like dear ? I got your number and I want to ask something about biodynamic farming.

I [01:30:23] Oh, no. Okay. So from my side, I think we're done. Thank you very much for your time and your whole knowledge. I think it was great. So I will have a lot of work to organize this, bring this together. Um, maybe one last question. If I have done the organisational part or the organisation part. Could I send it again to you to get your feedback? If I captured everything the way you thought I should capture it?

P2 [01:31:01] Yes.

P1 [01:31:03] Definitely.

I [01:31:04] Um, yeah. And I think. Then do you have any.

P1 [01:31:09] I'm so sorry for you that you're having to deal with this mess. But I'm sure you'll make it into something amazing.

I [01:31:19] Yeah, it's also super. And I mean, at some point, I think it's, it's also hard to stick completely to the system because it's also interesting to just let you talk and try to capture it at the same time because and also super interesting things come up. And so it's sometimes hard to find the balance. But yeah, I mean, I think I'm I'm happy.

P1 [01:31:48] P2 what's your farm called again? I forgot the name.

P2 [01:31:51] FARM NAME [? – name of P2's farm].

P1 [01:31:53] FARM NAME. Damn it.

P2 [01:31:54] For banks to communicate as the (incomprehensive – Dutch expression). Okay, so that's strange, but it is what it is.

I [01:32:04] Yeah. It's like I feel a little bit sorry that I took your time after this interview because we talked so much about time, and you need to spend time on your farm. And I'm like the researcher who takes your time.

P2 [01:32:20] No worries. I think this one is really different because I think it's really interesting to, um. Yeah, it's the question which I think we ourselves are working with all the time. Right.

I [01:32:33] Okay. Yeah. Okay, then it's good.

P2 [01:32:36] That's also, I think, why L. and M.. I don't know with whom you were working, I know. It is an interesting topic we should do something about. Like, what are these social tipping points?

P1 [01:32:50] Yeah.

P2 [01:32:53] Because my hope for the whole farming is not to be a farmer, but to get something going. You know.

I [01:33:00] Ah nice. Then I'm glad it's. Yeah, okay. Yeah. I mean, thank you so much.

P1 [01:33:11] It's really it's great to be a part of this as well. So don't worry and so I'm not really, so I don't have anything to say. I'm not really. I'm a part of the farm, but not a farmer. I don't dare to go as a farmer.

P2 [01:33:28] And I'm really curious to read what you made out of this and the whole research of course.

I [01:33:34] Yes. Yeah. I'm also still curious about that. Okay. So I have a good afternoon rest of the afternoon. And thank you so much again.

P1 [01:33:50] I'm gonna send you a message to plan a call.

P2 [01:33:53] Yeah. Cool.

P1 [01:33:56] After Earth Day, I haven't gotten back to you, but I will. Promise that again.

I [01:34:02] Okay. Nice. Have a good day.

P1 [01:34:06] Thanks so much.

P2 [01:34:08] Bye bye.